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DOES A MANDATORY BUT NON-BINDING TEST FOR ASPIRING STUDENTS IMPACT THE DIVERSITY IN AN ENGINEERING BACHELOR?

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ABSTRACT

Flanders, the Dutch-speaking part of Belgium, has a very open access to higher education. As a result universities have to accept any student with a secondary education diploma into the engineering bachelor, even if the secondary education program does not provide the required knowledge and competencies. To ensure that aspiring students are aware of the required level of mathematical problem solving skills, the universities are since 2013 organizing a non-mandatory and non-binding positioning test in the summer prior to entering higher education. In 2017, the Flemish government decided to make participation to a positioning test mandatory for aspiring engineering students from 2018 on. This mandatory participation could form an additional hurdle for aspiring students, which might impact students of minority groups. This is a concern as female students, pioneering students, and socio-economically challenged students are underrepresented in Flanders' engineering education, while industry still requires more engineers.

This paper is the first to study the impact on the diversity within the engineering program of the mandatory participation to the positioning test mandatory. This paper takes a quantitative yet descriptive approach and looks at the student population regarding gender, socio-economic status, pioneering status, and disability. The first results indicate that the extra hurdle of mandatory participation attracts more students and does not threaten the diversity in engineering bachelors. Furthermore, the mandatory participation to the positioning test did not affect the already better performance of female compared to male students, and reduced the performance gap for pioneering and learning-disabled students.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Gender and diversity in Engineering Bachelors

News regarding the need for engineers in our high-tech society is omnipresent. As no talent should be wasted in engineering education and as diversity can strengthen engineering education and practice, it is important to look at minority groups. Lent et al. present a social cognitive career development model for understanding three intricately linked aspects of career development: (a) the formation and elaboration of career-relevant interests, (b) selection of academic and career choice options, and (c) performance and persistence in educational and occupational pursuits [1]. The model shows that both personal, contextual, and experiential factors influence the career choice [1]. This paper focuses on female students, students with socio-economic challenges, pioneering students (students whose parents do not have a higher education degree), and students with disabilities. Gender and disability are included among the personal characteristics in Lent's model, while socio-economic status and pioneering status are included among the contextual characteristics. Female students are underrepresented in engineering studies in Europe as shown, among many, by the Attract project [2]. Interviews with engineering professors showed that, despite the underrepresentation of women, policies related to underrepresentation in undergraduate engineering programs are marginalized [3]. Blickenstaff [4] distinguishes six domains within the broad range of explanations in literature regarding the underrepresentation women in STEM: biological, lack of academic preparation, prior attitude, absence of role models, irrelevance of curricula for women, pedagogy tailored for men, chilly climate, cultural pressure for traditional role models, and an inherent masculine worldview inside science. He stresses the responsibility of all actors in the engineering education pipeline, and provides particular recommendations to reform STEM education [4]. Brainard & Carlin [5] found that a significant drop in academic self-confidence during their freshman year is often-occurring reason for female students to leave STEM programs. A Swedish study [6] showed that a competitive environment of STEM studies, the "chilly climate" female students perceive, and the stress they experience during studies can make them less confident in their STEM abilities and can increase the potential for dropping out. Beside gender. DeWitt et al. [7] found that ethnicity and cultural capital influence students' attitudes, experience, and participation of science in school and out of school. While less literature and data is available on the position of students with disabilities in engineering education, the Attract project [2] showed that, as for socio-economic factors, the proportion of students with disabilities in STEM faculties is lower in comparison to other faculties.

1.2 Admission and gender & diversity

Admission, and testing being often part of this, can be a potentially important, hurdle for aspiring engineering students. Within the social cognitive career development model, admission tests relate to both experiential and contextual factors [1]. High-stakes testing during admission have been shown to suffer from a gender and

diversity gap. This gap has been hypothesized to be wider in domains where a “fixed ability” (e.g. believing that success requires innate talent or natural genius) mindset was more common [8]. Even more, high-stake entrance tests strengthen the competitive atmosphere, which has been shown to be discouraging for female students [6]. The impact of gender on high stakes test score is complex. Casey et al. [10] for instance showed that spatial abilities and math self-confidence indirectly mediated relationship between gender and the high stakes test score (SAT in their study). Interestingly, using secondary school grades as a basis for admission has shown to introduce a bias in favour of women, while the reverse is true for standardized test scores [9]. Gender bias in the admission process can therefore strongly be influenced by the admission criteria [11]. Therefore bias can also be mitigated by adapting these admission criteria [11].

1.3 Context

Access to higher education in Flanders, the Dutch-speaking region in Belgium, is open: if students have a diploma of secondary education or a (foreign) diploma declared equivalent, they are directly admitted to any professional or academic bachelor's programme, with an exception for medicine, dentistry, and some programs in performing arts. Even for programs such as the Bachelor of Engineering Science, which rely on a strong mathematical prior skills, no formal requirements regarding students' prior education or mathematical proficiency can be formulated by the university. Together with the open-admission policy, low tuition fees (around 1000 euro for one academic year) are seen as important for the accessibility of higher education. On the negative side however, it results in a heterogeneous population regarding prior knowledge and skills, challenging teaching and guidance of especially first-year students. Students who do not have the required prior skills or motivation still enter the program, which contributes to a rather high drop-out rate of around 40% in the Bachelor of Engineering Science. Historically, the Engineering Science programs in Flanders did not have such an open-admission policy: until 2004 a multi-topic entrance exam existed for Engineering Science in Flanders, which assessed the mathematical prior skills of aspiring students. This entrance exam was believed to contribute to the high level of mathematics education in secondary schools, as it acted as a beacon for aspiring students and the schools of secondary education, and contributed to an international high reputation of the Flemish mathematics secondary school education [12]. After the abolishment of the entrance exam in 2014, a steady decrease of the first-year success rate was observed: from around 70% it dropped to less than 50%. In order to address the decreasing success rate all three Flemish universities with an Engineering Science bachelors in 2013 jointly installed a positioning test, which provides aspiring students with feedback on their mathematical skills and allows to compare their skill level with the required one [13]. The positioning test, called 'ijkingstoets' (www.ijkingstoets.be), is administered in the summer before entering higher education in two separate session. The multiple-choice test has around 30 mathematical problem solving, which the aspiring students solve in maximum four hours. The feedback aims at encouraging students

who succeed to subscribe in the program, stimulating students who are less successful to better prepare themselves by entering a remediation trajectory, and triggering reflection around the study choice for students who clearly lack the required skills. The score on the positioning test was found to be predictive for student success [14]. Furthermore it was shown that while female students on average score lower on the positioning test, their decision to enrol or not does not differ from male students [15]. The inclusive approach of the positioning test, by granting all participants more than enough time for completing the test, seemed to be successful as students with learning disabilities did not obtain lower scores on average [15]. After a decision of the Flemish Parliament, the positioning test became a “mandatory, non-binding entrance exam” in 2018, indicating that *participation* to the positioning test is mandatory for all aspiring students wanting to subscribe to the Bachelor Engineering Science, but that entrance to the program does not depend on the actual score on the test (non-binding). Each university has a committee who can grant exceptions for students who could, due to individual circumstances, not participate to the positioning test.

1.4 Research questions

The two research questions handled in this paper are: How does the mandatory participating to a test prior to entering an Engineering Bachelor program impact: (1) *the diversity* regarding gender, socio-economic status, pioneering status, and disability among new engineering bachelor students?; and (2) *the academic achievement of the diversity target groups?*

2 METHODOLOGY

This paper takes a quantitative approach to study the impact related to gender and diversity of the governmental decision, taken in 2018, to make participation to the positioning test mandatory for subscription in the Bachelor of Engineering Science in Flanders, Belgium. The study is performed for the Bachelor of Engineering Science of KU Leuven. Longitudinal data of the last 10 years was obtained in collaboration with the University’s central service on diversity, which provides detailed and fully anonymized yearly reports regarding gender and diversity of incoming students and how they progress in the program. This study focuses on generation students, these are students who subscribe to a higher education for the first time, and whom are therefore also the target audience of the positioning test. Typically, they constitute 96% of the students who enter the program. This paper focuses on: (1) **gender**, with a focus on female students; (2) **pioneering students**, students of whom neither parents has a diploma in higher education, (3) students with **socio-economic challenges** (scholarship, migrant background, and/or pioneering status)², and (4) students with a learning **disability**². The impact on the *diversity of the incoming population* is studied by monitoring the percentage of students that belong to each of the above target groups and by comparing it to the evolution of these target groups

² As the reporting of scholarship status and disabilities is only closed in June, no data for 2019 can be reported so far.

at the university level (same campus). The impact on the *academic achievement of the target groups* is studied by monitoring the percentage of students of the target groups that obtain a high study efficiency (obtained at least 80% of the credits after one year) and a low study efficiency (obtained less than 30% of the credits after one year), and by comparing it to the study efficiency of non-target group students.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Before digging deeper into gender and diversity, the **impact on the number of students** is reported. The year of the introduction of the mandatory participation the number of students suddenly decreased (-8.2%). One year later however, the largest increase in 10 years (+21.4%) was observed, resulting in the largest number of students (520) in the program since the start of the central reporting (2005). We can conclude that the introduction of the mandatory participation to the positioning test had a short-term negative effect, which was promptly recovered from, resulting in the end in attracting more students than before.

Fig. 1: Evolution over time of the percentage of particular target groups (a,b,c,d). The vertical grey bar represents the introduction of mandatory participation to the positioning test. Each of the top graphs shows the evolution of the percentage of students of a particular target group within the Engineering Science bachelor (blue line) compared to the percentage at university level at the same campus (grey line). The dashed line shows a linear fit to the before the introduction of the mandatory participation, allowing to check how the following years (2018, 2019) deviate from the expected trend-line. Each of

the bottom graphs shows the evolution of the difference between the percentage of students of that target group in the Bachelor of Engineering Science program and the university.

Fig. 1 visualizes the impact on the **representation of target groups**. The first year after the introduction of the mandatory participation to the positioning test the percentage of **female** students continued its slow but rather steady increase, resulting in the largest ever reported percentage of female students in 2018. Taking into account the overall decrease in student population in 2018 (Section 3.1) no change in the absolute number of female students was however observed with respect to 2017. We therefore conclude that female students were initially less influenced by this new hurdle to come to university than male students. In 2019 however, the percentage of female students again decreased, going back to the level of around 2015. In absolute numbers however, 2019 counted the largest number of female students since the beginning of the reporting. For the **pioneering** students, no deviation from the trend over the different years could be observed. For students with **socio-economic challenges**, until 2016 a steady decrease in the percentage of students with socio-economic challenges was observed, causing an increasing gap with the university level. One year after the introduction of the mandatory positioning test the percentage of students with socio-economic challenges suddenly increased up to the level of 2011. Despite the lower number of students in 2018, the absolute number of students with socio-economic challenges also increased after the introduction of the mandatory participation to the positioning test. Both at the university and at Engineering Science the percentage of students with **disabilities** is growing steadily over time. The introduction of the mandatory participation did not stop this trend. Even more, both the percentage of students with disabilities as the absolute number of students with disabilities has never been higher.

To study the impact of the mandatory participation of the positioning test on the **academic achievement** of the target groups we studied two indicators: the percentage of students with high study efficiency ($\geq 80\%$, Fig. 2) and low study efficiency ($< 30\%$, Fig. 3). Study efficiency is the ratio of the successfully obtained credits points and the total number of booked credits points (typically 60). **Female** students are in general, despite being underrepresented in the program overall, overrepresented in the high-achieving group (Fig. 2a) and underrepresented in the low-achieving group (Fig. 3a): on average they perform better in Engineering Science than male students. The introduction of the mandatory participation to the positioning test did not break this trend. In contrast to female students, **pioneering** students are underrepresented in the high-achieving group (Fig. 2b) and overrepresented in the low-achieving group (Fig. 3b). For these students, the positioning test had a positive impact: the gap between the academic achievement, hereafter referred to as the performance gap, of pioneering and non-pioneering students decreased. The decrease in the percentage of pioneering students with low study efficiencies especially contrasts with the increase of the percentage of non-pioneering students with low study efficiencies. The positioning test decreased, but not yet eliminated the performance gap. For students with **socio-economic**

challenges, who as pioneering students are underrepresented in the underrepresented in the high-achieving group (Fig. 2c) and overrepresented in the low-achieving group (Fig. 3c), the impact is less clear. The gap in the high-achieving group increased, while the gap in the low-achieving group decreased. Further monitoring is required to understand the impact on this student group. For students with **disabilities** the impact was so far remarkable. Historically, students with disabilities were underrepresented in the high-achieving group (Fig. 2c) and overrepresented in the low-achieving group (Fig. 3c). In 2018 however, since the first time ever, the percentage of high-achieving students was higher in the group of students with disabilities than in the group of students without disabilities. The closing of the performance gap was already achieved in 2017 for the low-achieving students, in 2018 this positive trend continued: for the second year in a row the percentage of low-achieving students within the students with disabilities was lower than the percentage of low-achieving students within the students without disabilities.

Fig. 2: Evolution over time of the percentage of students of a particular target group (a,b,c,d) with high study efficiency (i.e. obtained $\geq 80\%$ of the credits) after one year. The vertical grey bar represents the introduction of mandatory participation to the positioning test prior to academic year 2018. Each of the top graphs shows the evolution within the bachelor of Engineering Science of a particular target group (green line) compared to the remaining part of the study population (blue line). The dashed green line shows a linear fit to the target group for the years before the introduction of the mandatory participation, allowing to check how the following years (2018, 2019) deviate from the expected trend-line. Each of the bottom graphs shows the evolution of performance gap, the difference between the

percentages of students with high efficiency of the target group compared to the percentage of students with high study efficiency of students who are not in the target group.

4 SUMMARY

This paper used a quantitative and descriptive approach to study the impact on diversity of the governmental decision to make participation to the positioning test mandatory for aspiring engineering students. At the global population level an obligatory but non-binding entrance test was found, despite an effect in the first year, not to hinder entrance to an Engineering Science bachelor program and even result in a growing student population. As

Fig. 3: Evolution over time of the percentage of students of a particular target group (a,b,c,d) that obtained a low study efficiency (i.e. obtained <30% of the credits) after one year. For more information regarding the graphical representation see the caption of Fig. 2.

the representation of students with socio-economic challenges and disabilities increased, the mandatory participation to the positioning test was no hurdle to them. While the representation of pioneering students seemed to be unchanged, two years after the introduction of the positioning test the percentage of female students, while still increased in absolute numbers, decreased. Therefore, in the future particular attention should be spent to the representation of female and pioneering student. Regarding academic achievement the mandatory participation to the positioning test

did not influence the better performance of female compared to male students, and reduced the gap for pioneering and learning-disabled students. Notable, for the first time ever high-achieving were more frequent and low-achieving students were less frequent among students with disabilities compared students without disabilities. For socio-economically challenged students the picture is mixed: while the gap in low-achievement was reduced, the gap in high-achievement increased. Therefore, in the future particular attention should be spend to the achievement of students with socio-economic challenges.

The paper has some limitations. As the mandatory participation to the positioning test was only introduced two years ago, only data of two years and even one year for student performance, was available. The upcoming academic years have to show if the observed trends will persist. So far, only a descriptive analysis of the data was performed without statistical tests. As data of more academic year is available such a statistical analysis will become a valuable next step. Furthermore, a qualitative study using interviews with positioning test participants and students would help to interpret the trends and shed light on individual student trajectories.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lent, R. W., Brown, S. D., & Hackett, G. (2000). Contextual supports and barriers to career choice: a social cognitive analysis. *Journal of counseling psychology*, 47(1), 36–49.
- [2] Attract project: Enhancing the attractiveness of studies in science and technology; Full Report (2012), <http://attractproject.org>
- [3] Beddoes, K. (2016). Selling policy short? Faculty perspectives on the role of policy in addressing women's underrepresentation in engineering education, *Studies in Higher Education*, 10.1080/03075079.2016.1266610, 43, 9, 1561–1572.
- [4] Blickenstaff, C. J. (2005). Women and science careers: leaky pipeline or gender filter? *Gender and Education*, 17(4), 369–386.
- [5] Brainard, S. G., & Carlin, L. (1998). A Six-Year Longitudinal Study of Undergraduate Women in Engineering and Science. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 87(4), 17–27.
- [6] Chang Rundgren, S.-N., Sun, Y., & Jidesjö, A. (2019). Examining Gender Differences in Students' Entrance into and Persistence in STEM Programs in Swedish Higher Education. *European Journal of Educational Sciences*, 6(1), 66–94. <https://doi.org/10.19044/ejes.v6no1a5>
- [7] DeWitt, J., Archer, L., Osborne, J., Dillon, J., Willis, B., & Wong, B. (2011). High aspirations but low progression: the science aspirations–careers paradox amongst minority ethnic students. *International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 9(2), 243–271.
- [8] Leslie, S.-J., Cimpian, A., Meyer, M., Freeland, E., Expectations of brilliance underlie gender distributions across academic disciplines, *Science* 16 Jan 2015, Vol. 347, Issue 6219, pp. 262-265, DOI: 10.1126/science.1261375

- Razia Azen , Shmuel Bronner & Naomi Gafni (2002) Examination of Gender Bias in University Admissions, *Applied Measurement in Education*, 15:1, 75-94, DOI: 10.1207/S15324818AME1501_05
- Casey, M.B., Nuttall, R.L., Pezaris, E. Mediators of gender differences in mathematics college entrance test scores: a comparison of spatial skills with internalized beliefs and anxieties. (1997) *Dev Psychol.* 33(4), 669–680. doi:10.1037//0012-1649.33.4.669
- Holloway, B.M., Reed, T., Imbrie, P.K. and Reid, K. (2014), Research-Informed Policy Change: A Retrospective on Engineering Admissions. *J. Eng. Educ.*, 103: 274-301. doi:10.1002/jee.20046
- PISA Technical Report 2003 <http://www.pisa.oecd.org/document/13/0,3343>
- [13] Vandewalle, J.P.L. and Callens R. (2013), A positioning test mathematics in Flanders for potential academic engineering students, Proc. of the 41st SEFI Conference, Leuven, Belgium
- [14] Vanderroost, J., Callens, R., Vandewalle, J., De Laet, T. (2014). Engineering positioning test in Flanders : a powerful predictor for study success ? In: Proc. of the 42nd Annual Conference, (1-8). Presented at the SEFI 2014, Birmingham, UK, 15 Sep 2014-19 Sep 2014.
- [15] Vanderroost, J., Callens, R., Vandewalle, J., De Laet, T. (2014). Diversity and the academic engineering positioning test in Flanders: Impact on female students and students with disabilities. In: Proceedings of the 42rd Annual SEFI Conference, (Paper No. 112), (1-8). Presented at the SEFI conference, Birmingham, UK, 15 Sep 2014-19 Sep 2014.